

Application of Infrared Spectroscopy to Erodibility Studies of the Soil

SUBHASH CHANDRA and S. K. DE

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad

Manuscript received 27 April 1973; accepted 21 June 1973

The IR-absorption spectra of un-eroded and eroded soils of semi-desert, arid, semi-arid, sub-humid, Vindhyan and Bundelkhand soil-climatic regions of Uttar Pradesh, India were taken by KBr-Mull technique on Perkin-Elmer infra-red spectrophotometer. This technique has been found useful in characterizing eroded and un-eroded soils and also in differentiating more erodible soils from erosion resistant ones.

DE^{5,6} discovered that infra-red absorption spectra of the soil between 2.0 μ 15.0 μ can be used for studying various physico-chemical properties and general fertility status of the soil. They proposed that IR peaks at different wavelengths can be correlated with one or the other soil property. The peaks between 2.0 to 3.0 μ have relation with adsorbed (bonded) water, 3.0 to 7.0 μ , with absorbed (un-bonded) water and may also indicate B.E.C. of the soil; 9.0 to 9.5 μ with Si-O bond; 9.5 to 10.0 μ with Al-O bond; 10.9 to 11.0 μ with Si-H bond; and 12.0 to 15.0 μ with Si-C bond. Depth and sharpness of a particular peak may speak quantitatively the contents of that of the constituents of the functional groups. It, therefore, appears to be relevant to suggest that IR absorption spectra can be successfully used for rapid soil testing work.

The application of infrared spectrophotometry may also provide a simple and rapid method to test the erodibility behaviour of the soil by water. The objectives of the present study are thus (1) to investigate if the infrared spectra of un-eroded soil is different from eroded soil and (2) to see if this simple technique can be utilized for predicting a more erodible soil from the soil resistant to erosion by water.

Experimental

The soils used for this investigation were collected out of 0-20 cms, depth from (1) eroded and (2) un-eroded sites of the same locality belonging to a particular soil-climatic region. Different type of soil were collected from (1) semi-desert (Agra), (2) arid

TABLE I—COMPOSITION AND SOME OTHER PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS

Properties	Agra (Semi-desert)		Allahabad (arid)		Saharanpur (semi-arid)		Gorakhpur (sub-humid)		Mirzapur (Vindhyan)		Jhansi (Bundelkhand)	
	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded
<i>Mechanical Analysis</i>												
Coarse sand	0.29	1.20	0.48	0.72	0.69	1.32	0.33	0.98	0.95	1.37	0.62	0.97
Fine sand	76.33	70.71	57.15	66.39	77.34	63.98	72.49	60.88	45.43	44.08	28.81	32.17
Silt	12.13	17.49	28.40	19.25	12.73	17.47	15.05	22.11	20.92	39.49	32.14	22.80
Clay	10.30	9.75	13.59	13.11	9.66	18.17	11.73	14.12	30.90	12.60	38.39	43.58
Cation exchange capacity (m.s./100 g.soil)	9.95	9.45	12.80	11.60	8.25	14.10	10.65	11.25	10.50	13.80	26.00	28.65
Sesquioxide p.c.	5.75	6.50	7.35	8.50	4.00	6.55	5.15	5.90	8.85	10.75	13.50	13.75
Calcium p.c.(CaO)	0.16	0.23	0.34	0.41	0.14	0.25	0.17	0.21	0.23	0.25	0.93	0.94
Calcium+magnesium p.c.	1.41	1.58	1.14	1.36	0.64	1.00	0.67	0.71	0.88	1.00	2.98	3.09
Total organic carbon p.c.	0.14	0.11	0.27	0.20	0.20	0.15	0.35	0.26	0.41	0.35	0.36	0.32
pH	7.70	9.30	7.30	7.20	7.50	7.50	7.10	7.60	6.70	7.00	9.00	9.10
<i>Erosion coefficient</i>												
(1) at 1% slope	33.88	32.80	30.06	33.46	19.31	13.17	20.21	15.47	8.27	13.06	5.71	7.82
(2) at 2% slope	56.28	55.50	40.58	57.29	19.88	16.35	41.53	33.95	10.52	15.51	8.90	9.60
(3) at 4% slope	92.61	80.20	71.13	80.91	42.52	34.90	63.23	43.96	17.41	20.43	10.51	14.05
(4) at 8% slope	149.00	126.59	97.39	141.26	87.69	45.24	107.72	71.60	20.35	26.10	13.10	17.73
Erosion ratio	98.62	82.75	52.49	84.17	55.57	18.43	64.93	39.58	13.96	16.00	4.80	6.03

(Allahabad), (3) semi-arid (Saharanpur), (4) sub-humid (Gorakhpur), (5) Vindhyan (Mirzapur) and, (6) Bundelkhand (Jhansi), soil-climatic regions of Uttar Pradesh, India (Raychaudhury, 1963). The climatic parameters of these regions are given below :

The physico-chemical analysis of these samples was done by usual procedures^{1,2,3}. Relative erodibility in terms of "erosion coefficients" was measured by De-Subhash Erosion Apparatus⁴. Erosion coefficient is positively correlated with the erodibility of the soil (Table 1).

CLIMATIC PARAMETERS OF THE SAMPLING SITES

Soil climatic regions	Elevation above sea level (ft.)	Max. temp. (°F)	Min. temp. (°F)	Mean Temp. corrected (°F)	Mean relative humidity corrected (%)	Rainfall (inches)
Semi-desert	555	90.7	67.6	78.4	53.8	25.56
Arid	307	90.2	66.8	77.3	61.3	39.16
Semi-arid	887	87.2	62.6	73.5	60.6	42.30
Sub-humid	256	88.0	67.4	76.6	67.8	50.77
Vidhyan	—	—	—	77.3	—	42.68
Bundelkhand	855	91.2	69.0	79.2	52.3	37.57

TABLE 2—IR-CURVES OF SOME UN-ERODED AND ERODED SOILS OF UTTAR PRADESH (INDIA)

Soils	Wavelength (μ)														
	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0	9.0	10.0	11.0	12.0	13.0	14.0	15.0	
Un-eroded or Eroded															
Agra : Un-eroded	2.750 2.925	3.450	4.325	5.250 5.650	6.200 6.450	7.200		9.001 9.800	10.950		12.450 12.750		14.400		
Eroded	2.800	3.250	4.300 4.900	5.250 5.600	6.125	7.100		9.075 9.350		11.000	12.450 12.850		14.300		
Allahabad : Un-eroded	2.800 2.950	3.450 3.850	4.300	5.000	6.200 6.575 6.900	7.250		9.000 9.850	10.150	11.000 11.300 11.500	12.450 12.875	13.400 13.850	14.450		
Eroded	2.800	3.300 3.450	4.350	5.300 5.650	6.150	7.200		9.150 9.450 9.850		11.000	12.450 12.950	13.850	14.400		
Saharanpur : Un-eroded	2.750 2.900	3.450 3.950		5.000 5.300 5.500 5.950	6.100 6.650 6.875 7.850	7.200 7.675		9.200 9.850		11.000	12.450 12.850		14.400		
Eroded	2.750 2.950		4.350	5.225 5.550 5.750	6.150 6.900	7.200 7.725		9.050 9.850	10.950		12.500		14.350		
Gorakhpur : Un-eroded	2.800 2.950	3.200 3.450 3.800	4.900	5.000 5.275 5.600	6.000 6.100 6.900	7.000 7.200 7.650 7.750		9.050 9.900		11.000	12.450 12.750		14.350		
Eroded	2.350	3.250 3.450	4.950	5.275	6.150 6.900	7.200		9.150 9.875		11.000	12.450 12.750		14.350		
Mirzapur : Un-eroded	2.750	3.000 3.250 3.700		5.000 5.300 5.600 5.750 5.950	6.100 6.850	7.250 7.650	8.100 8.300 8.925	9.200 9.800	10.995		12.500 12.875	13.300	14.375		
Eroded	2.750 2.950	3.150 3.400	4.950	5.250 5.500	6.100	7.175 7.750	8.900	9.950	10.600 10.900		12.650		14.300		
Jhansi : Un-eroded	2.725 2.950	3.225 3.425 3.600	4.250	5.300 5.750 5.950	6.100 6.800 6.950	7.150 7.700 7.825	8.950	9.850	10.950		12.400 11.350 12.800	13.150	14.350		
Eroded	2.750 2.950	3.250 3.350	4.250	5.350	6.100 6.900	7.000 7.200	8.950	9.850	10.750	11.400	12.450 12.800		14.300		

TABLE 3—TOTAL NUMBER OF PEAKS AND THEIR DISTRIBUTION IN DIFFERENT REGIONS OF IR-CURVE

Place	Soil	Total No. of peaks	No. of peaks in different regions		
			2.0 μ to 7.0 μ	8.0 μ to 11.0 μ	12.0 μ to 15.0 μ
Agra (Semi-desert)	Un-eroded	16	10	3	3
	Eroded	14	8	3	3
Allahabad (Arid)	Un-eroded	21	10	6	5
	Eroded	16	8	4	4
Saharanpur (Semi-arid)	Un-eroded	20	14	3	3
	Eroded	15	10	3	2
Gorakhpur (Sub-humid)	Un-eroded	22	16	3	3
	Eroded	14	8	3	3
Mirzapur (Vindhyan)	Un-eroded	23	13	6	4
	Eroded	16	10	4	2
Janshi (Bundel- khand).	Un-eroded	23	15	4	4
	Eroded	18	11	4	3

The infra-red absorption spectra of the soil passed through 100-mesh (B.S.) sieve was taken between 2.0 μ to 15.0 μ by KBr-mull technique on Perkin Elmer infra-red spectrophotometer in moisture free atmosphere.

Results and Discussion

The IR-curves of different un-eroded and eroded soils are given in Figs. 1-6 and their peaks are tabulated in Table 2. The total number of peaks and their distribution in different functional regions of the IR-absorption spectra are given in Table 3.

Characterisation of Un-eroded and Eroded soils by IR Spectra :

It is interesting to note that IR curves of un-eroded soils of all the soil climatic regions have greater number of peaks than the corresponding eroded soils. This is in conformity with De⁵ who observed that fertile soils have comparatively greater number of peaks than the infertile soils. Eroded soils are, generally, known to be less fertile due to physical removal of fine soil particles, nutrients and

Fig. 1. Agra Soil

Fig. 2. Allahabad Soil

Fig. 3. Saharanpur Soil

Fig. 4. Gorakhpur Soil

Fig. 5. Mirzapur Soil

Fig. 6. Jhansi Soil

organic matter etc., and thus result in lower number of IR-peaks.

De⁶ assigned the regions of 2.0μ to 7.0μ to bonded and un-bonded water; 8.0μ to 11.0μ to silica, alumina, and pH; and 12.0μ to 15.0μ to Si-C bond indicating organic matter status of the soil. The values of total number of peaks given in Table 3 and the groups 2.0μ to 7.0μ and 12.0μ to 15.0μ clearly indicate the role of water absorption capacity and soil organic matter on soil erosion by water. The values for eroded soils under these two heads are lower than the corresponding values of the un-eroded soils, clearly indicating the presence of not as much amount of organic matter and those factors in them which contribute to greater water absorption by soil. Workers like Bennett⁷ and Stallings⁸ have clearly shown the importance of these two important factors in checking soil erosion. The total number of peaks obtained in the region 8.0μ to 11.0μ which indicate silica, alumina and pH, do not show much difference and, therefore, it can not be said with definiteness if these factors which also contribute equally to the erosion of the soils of these regions, can be studied with equal accuracy by this new technique.

Characterization of more erodible and erosion resistant soils by IR-spectra :

The observation of IR-curves (Figs. 1-6) and the nature of their peaks will show interesting characteristics which can make IR-spectrophotometry of soils a useful technique for characterizing more erodible soils from erosion resistant soils.

A perusal of IR-curves at 3.0μ in un-eroded soils will show that the peak at the wavelength is sharp and deep in less erodible or erosion resistant soils of Bundelkhand and Vindhyan regions (compare erosion coefficient of soils in Table 1). In other cases of semi-desert, arid, semi-arid and sub-humid regions, where soils are more erodible, this peak is shallow and blunt. Secondly, in more erodible soils, the transmittance of the peak at 10.0μ wavelength of un-eroded soil is more than 15%. It is true in semi-desert, arid and semi-arid soils. Less erodible soils generally have this transmittance between 0-15. And then, as a general feature, the erosion resistant soils have comparatively more number of well-defined and sharp peaks than soils which are highly erodible in nature.

References

1. M. L. JACKSON, Soil Chemical Analysis, Asia Publishing House, Calcutta, 1958.
2. C. S. PIPER, Soil and Plant Analysis, University of Adelaide, 1950.
3. S. K. DE, Methods of Soil Analysis Narayan Publishing House, Allahabad, India, 1962.
4. S. CHANDRA and S. K. DE, Effect of protein on soil erosion by water, *Anales de Edafologia Y. Agrobiologia* (in press), 1972.
5. S. K. DE, Infra-red curve of fertile and intertile soils, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1968, 3, 58.
6. S. K. DE, Infra red spectra of Indian Soils, Part I, *Indian J., Agri. Chem.*, 1968, 1, 12.
7. H. H. BENNETT, Soil Conservation, McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., 1939.
8. J. H. STALLINGS, Soil Conservation, Prentice Hall, Inc., 1962.
9. S. P. RAYCHAUDHURY, soils of India, ICAR Publication, 1963.